
234. Ultra-faint dwarf galaxies

THE FIRST TWO dwarf spheroidal galaxies (dSph) in the Local Group, Sculptor and Fornax, were identified by Harlow Shapley in 1938. But until around 2000, their rarity seemed in conflict with Λ CDM cosmology, which predicted that massive galaxies like the Milky Way should be surrounded by many dark-matter dominated satellite halos. Over the past 25 years, this conflict eased with the discovery of many more, by SDSS and others.

One of Gaia's earliest contributions to their properties (Helmi et al., 2018) involved determination of the orbits of the nine 'classical' dwarf spheroidal galaxies (Carina, Draco, Fornax, Leo I, Leo II, Sagittarius, Sculptor, Sextans, Ursa Minor), which I detailed in essay 31. Since then, and as I described in essay 231, Gaia's parallaxes and proper motions have been used to characterise their orbits, structure, internal kinematics, and bulk rotation; the correlation of their star formation episodes with their close orbital approaches to the Milky Way; and the nature of their accompanying globular clusters.

THE DISTINCT CLASS of *ultra-faint* dwarf galaxies was first mentioned (I believe) in 2005, with the discovery, from SDSS, of an unusually extended object (Willman I), at 45 kpc distance, with properties intermediate between those of globular clusters and dwarf galaxies (Willman et al., 2005a). The authors commented that: *'If it is a dwarf spheroidal, then it is the faintest yet known by two orders of magnitude, and is the first example of the ultra-faint dwarfs predicted by some theories.'*

A second, in Ursa Major at a distance of 100 kpc, also from SDSS, was reported by Willman et al. (2005b). This was followed by several others, including other companions to the Milky Way, in Canes Venatici at 220 kpc (Zucker et al., 2006), and in Boötes at 60 kpc (Belokurov et al., 2006). Others have since been found in the vicinity of the Magellanic Clouds (Koposov et al., 2015).

These ultra-faint dwarfs contain from a few hundred to $\sim 10^5$ stars, and have luminosities $\lesssim 10^5 L_\odot$. While often resembling globular clusters in appearance, they are more extended, and with more dark matter (and more than in dwarf spheroidals), with typical $M/L \gtrsim 100$.

THE CURRENT PICTURE is that these ultra-faint dwarfs represent the faintest ($M_V \gtrsim -6$), most metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -2$), and most dark matter-dominated end of the dwarf galaxy spectrum (Willman & Strader, 2012). As the oldest and least chemically evolved systems known, they provide *'unique windows into the formation of the first galaxies, and the behaviour of dark matter on small scales'* (Simon, 2019). Formed only a few million years after the Big Bang, before reionisation, they provide important constraints on Λ CDM predictions (e.g., Bovill & Ricotti, 2009; Koposov et al., 2009; Li et al., 2010; Brooks et al., 2013; Sawala et al., 2016; Wetzel et al., 2016).

Galaxies close to the division between the classical dwarf spheroidals and these ultra-faint dwarfs include Antlia II and Crater II, which I discussed in essay 128. Their orbits, characterised by Gaia, are enabling studies of their mass loss, tidal evolution, and possible relationship to the Galaxy's disk warp (e.g. Vivas et al., 2020b).

OVER THE VARIOUS data releases, Gaia-based studies have been reported for a number of ultra-faint dwarf galaxies, amongst them Boötes I, Boötes III, Coma Ber, Eridanus II, Eridanus IV, Grus II, Hercules, Horologium I, Hydrus I, Leo V, Pegasus III, Pegasus IV, Pisces II, Reticulum II, Segue I, Segue II, Tucana II, Tucana III, Ursa Major I, and Ursa Major II.

These studies have targeted improved membership, as a first step in the most important goal of determining their improved orbits around the Galaxy. The orbits are of particular diagnostic value: they provide fundamental constraints on the mass and shape of the Milky Way halo, on their evolution and tidal disruption, on the connection between their orbits and their star formation histories, and ultimately how our Galaxy has assembled its population of dwarf galaxy satellites, and how this relates to the Galaxy's large-scale environment.

Helmi et al. (2018) considered Boötes I as the best of these for study with Gaia DR2, given its relatively well-populated red giant branch, and its relatively proximity, at 60 kpc. They determined a distance accurate to around 2 kpc, and a space velocity accurate to 20 km s^{-1} .

Final membership selection for three ultra-faint dwarf galaxies. Cyan circles indicate the initial candidate members from spectroscopy. The final distance cut has not been applied, but is shown by the red circles. From Massari & Helmi (2018), Figure 2.

ON THE DETERMINATION of bulk space motions of dwarf galaxies in general, Gaia DR2 ‘has started a revolution’ (Fritz et al., 2018). Based on careful membership selection, starting with initial guesses but refined using Gaia DR2 astrometry and photometry (see figure above), Massari & Helmi (2018) derived absolute proper motions for seven ultra-faint dwarf galaxies within 70 kpc (Boötes III, Carina II, Grus II, Reticulum II, Sagittarius II, Segue II, and Tucana IV).

Gaia DR2 and DR3 proper motions have now been used to establish memberships and distances for many other systems, including Tucana II (Chiti et al., 2020), Hercules (Mutlu-Pakdil et al., 2020), and Ursa Major I, Coma Berenices, and Boötes I (Waller et al., 2023).

RIGOROUS MEMBERSHIP selection is essential for characterising the morphologies, and identifying possible extensions attributable to tidal disruption. Such extended morphologies have now been reported for Leo V (Mutlu-Pakdil et al., 2019), Hercules (Mutlu-Pakdil et al., 2020), Eridanus IV (Cerny et al., 2021), and Boötes I (Filion & Wyse, 2021).

Searching for RR Lyrae variables in the vicinity of these satellite galaxies provides a particularly powerful method for suppressing foreground contamination, and hence identifying potential extra-tidal members.

Searches in 27 nearby (< 100 kpc) ultra-faint dwarfs by Vivas et al. (2020a) associated 47 Gaia RR Lyrae stars with 14 different satellite galaxies, identifying extra-tidal RR Lyrae in six (three with extra-tidal stars in addition to members within their tidal radius: Boötes I, Boötes III and Sagittarius II; and three in which the galaxy itself does not contain any RR Lyrae: Tucana III, Eridanus III, and Reticulum III). They inferred that these galaxies may also be undergoing tidal disruption. Similarly, Tau et al. (2024) found seven new RR Lyrae stars in six ultra-faint dwarf galaxies (Hydrus I, Ursa Major I, Ursa Major II, Grus II, Eridanus II, and Tucana II).

ACCURATE BULK PROPER MOTIONS, and hence accurate orbits, provide the ingredients for computing their orbital histories.

Amongst these, Gaia EDR3 proper motions for Eridanus II suggest that it is on its first infall into the Milky Way (Fu et al., 2022). In the case of the distant but closely separated (40 kpc) systems Pegasus III and Pisces II, the

study by Richstein et al. (2022) found no morphological features indicating that a significant interaction between the two has occurred. Propagating their orbits in a combined Milky Way–LMC potential, they found a possible orbital history in which they experienced a close (10–20 kpc) mutual passage a little more than 1 Gyr ago, followed by a combined passage around the Large Magellanic Cloud (30–60 kpc) just under 1 Gyr ago. If confirmed, they would add to the rare occurrence of coherent satellite pairs within the Local Group.

For the newly discovered Pegasus IV, Cerny et al. (2023) determined an elliptical retrograde orbit, currently near its orbital apocentre.

Foote et al. (2025) showed that the ultra-faint dwarf Segue II had a recent (77 ± 5 Myr ago) close flyby with the Cetus–Palca halo stream, within the stream’s 2σ width. They show that this interaction potentially enables constraints on its mass and density profile at much larger, kpc-scale, radii than are probed by its stars.

THERE IS A CONNECTION between the orbits of satellite galaxies and their star-formation histories (Grebel, 2001; Tolstoy et al., 2009). This has been nicely demonstrated in the study of the orbits of the classical dwarf spheroidals by Miyoshi & Chiba (2020). These authors showed that their infall time, defined as when the satellite galaxy first crosses within the growing virial radius of the Milky Way’s halo, coincides well with the peak star-formation rate, as a consequence of ram pressure on their gas content.

In contrast, the general consensus is that star-formation activity in ultra-faint dwarfs had already peaked prior to their infall times, possibly suppressed at the epoch of reionization of the Universe (Okamoto et al., 2008; Brown et al., 2012; Brown et al., 2014; Weisz et al., 2015; Simon, 2019).

ULTRA-FAINT GALAXIES provide specific challenges to the gravitational theory of Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND) as a (non-dark matter) explanation for the rotation curve of galaxies (e.g. Safarzadeh & Loeb, 2021; Sánchez Almeida, 2022). In this context, arguments against MOND relate to the observed velocity dispersion, infall history, and observed tidal features, established by Gaia, for Ursa Major I, Willman I, and Tucana III (Safarzadeh & Loeb, 2021).